

Research on the personality and Teaching Role Design of Animated Pedagogical Agent of AR Books in the Context of Metaverse

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 26 , 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 27, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching, Role Design, Animated Pedagogical Agent</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7775282</p>	<p><i>The presence of proxies, either animated or static images, positively affects users in the learning environment. Images of both static and dynamic agents are considered more plausible than the absence of images. Regarding the perception of an agent as a person, animated agents have a positive effect on static images. Lester, Kahler, Barlow, Stone and Bhogal (1997) found that the presence of animated instructional agents had a significant, strong and positive effect on students' perceptions of their learning experiences. In their study, middle school student participants encountered one of five "cloned" agents. These agents differed in the way they expressed themselves and in the level of advice they provided in response to the students' problem-solving activities.</i></p>

Introduction

There were three types of communication styles: short animated clips incorporating animated objects (e.g., plants and verbal descriptions to convey principle-based advice about the object), verbal advice without accompanying animation, and direct and task-specific verbal advice. These five factors were expressed as fully expressed, principle-based animation/language, principle-based language, task-specific language, or silent cloning conditions. The agent remains on the screen throughout the learning process. At the end of the module, students were asked to assess their perceptions of the agent's affective features (encouragement, utility, trustworthiness, and clarity). The overall results suggest that the effect of realistic agent roles in an interactive learning environment can have a positive impact on students' perceptions. This positive effect of agent roles can even occur when the agent is not expressive, such as in a muted state. The subjective assessment in this study had eight questions, and participants rated all five items on a mean scale ranging from 3.0 (neither good nor bad) to 4.6 (very good). There was no (poor) scale to assess any agent cloning, which refers to the strong influence of the agent's role on the learner (Lester, Converse, Kahler, Barlow, Stone, & Bhogal, 1997). In another experiment, Moreno, Reislein and Ozogul (2010) recruited secondary school students. Students were randomly divided into three treatment groups: students without visual APA and guided by voice only (group C), animated arrows pointing simultaneously with verbal explanations (group A), and peer-agent directed movements accompanying verbal explanations (group P). The narratives were identical for all three groups. The results showed that group (P) had significantly higher post-test scores than groups (A) and (C). Group (P) also significantly and highly reported that the participants liked the agent the most. Thus, APA may elicit more attention than arrow symbols due to the social stimulation of the agent. Furthermore, learning gains in the agent group were consistent with a role effect that positively influenced learners' perceptions of the learning experience and allowed them to perceive it (Moreno, Reislein, & Ozogul, 2010). In addition, one study examined the effects of agent image and animation on learners' perceptions of the educational agent role, i.e., the extent to which the agent was a human-like, credible, engaging, and instructor-like person (Baylor & Ryu, 2003). To achieve this goal, a 25-item survey, the Agent Persona Role Instrument, was used. Seventy-five preservice teachers were recruited and randomly divided into three treatment groups: a fully animated proxy group, a static proxy image group, and a no-proxy group. In all three cases, several features were the same: voices, suggestions, and peak bubbles displaying verbally suggested text. After completing the agent-based environment, participants were asked to rate the perceived agent character features. Results indicated that the presence of an animated agent had a strong positive impact, causing the animated agent to be perceived as attractive and lecturer-like.

Literature Review

APA may elicit more attention than arrow symbols due to the social stimulation of the agent. The learning benefits of the agent group are consistent with the persona effect, which positively influences learners' perceptions of the learning experience and engages them cognitively (Moreno, Reislein, & Ozogul, 2010). In addition, one study examined the effects of agent image and animation on learners' perceptions of the educational agent role, i.e., the extent to which the agent is a human-like, credible, engaging, and teacher-like person (Baylor & Ryu, 2003).

The above results suggest that using animated agents and showing them during learning can positively influence the learning outcomes of learners who are perceived as engaging and teacher-like, in addition to the fact that the presence of animated teaching agents positively influences learners' perceptions of the perceived subject.

The effect of animated teaching agents on learning outcomes

A natural question for any new feature in a multimedia-based teaching and learning environment is the impact of that feature on knowledge acquisition. Research on the use of animated teaching agents for teaching in China began with the introduction of teaching agent technology into online teaching systems proposed by Kaiquan Chen and Yi Li (2002), and then Xueying Li (2007) studied the learning effects by analyzing students' memory scores and transfer scores using homemade interactive multimedia courseware based on research on relevant strategies such as reflection and instruction, and the experimental results showed that in interactive media learning The experimental results showed that the use of instructional agents in interactive media learning could significantly improve the memory and transfer performance of students in poor classes. Based on the research results related to child psychology, Xu Fei (2009) combined virtual characters with multimedia design, when virtual characters are like playmates who can live and learn with children, so when creating virtual animated characters, they should have psychological soothing, establish a positive character image and give children users a sense of security and trust, which can help children complete their learning tasks more efficiently; Zheng Jun (2012) investigated the role of animated teaching agents in multimedia video learning using eye-movement technology, and by analyzing the number of eye movements and time results of the subjects, it was concluded that adding animated teaching agents helped to improve correctness and maintain quiz scores compared to no animated teaching agents; S. Li (2017) used the cost of agent creation as an entry point to investigate the animated teaching agents through self-made static and dynamic teaching PPTs learning effect and the effect of learning motivation were investigated, and the experiment illustrated that the introduction of teaching agents in the form of learning, both dynamic and static forms of teaching agents can promote students' learning performance.

In general, the research on animation teaching agents in the teaching field in China is mainly based on theoretical analysis of functional positioning and design framework, and the empirical research for effective verification is obviously insufficient compared with foreign countries.

The current empirical studies on animated teaching agents have diverse opinions about the effect of teaching agents on learners' learning outcomes (Johnson & Rubin, 2011; Heidig & Clarebout, 2011; Li & Kizilcec, 2016; Dincer & Doganay, 2016). Some researchers have taken a negative attitude towards learning with media, arguing that while animated instructional agents have a positive impact on students with low prior knowledge, there may be some negative impact on students with high prior knowledge (Johnson, Ozogul, & Reislein, 2015), and, some other studies have found that adding animated instructional agents to multimedia does not promote learners' learning outcomes (Frechette & Moreno, 2010). For example, in studies on listening anxiety and comprehension, there was no significant difference in the effect of having animated teaching agents on learners' learning outcomes (ko, 2010). Similarly, Domagk (2010) stated that attractive agents promote learner learning, but unattractive instructional agents not only do not result in better learning outcomes for learners, but can even hinder learning. However, there is growing evidence that animated instructional agents pedagogical tools have a positive impact on learning using multimedia modules, and that adding animated instructional agents makes computer systems more user-friendly, engaging, and motivating (Baylor & Amy, 2011; Romero-Hall, Watson, Adcock, Bliss, & Adams, 2016; Lawson, Alyssa, Mayer, Adamo-Villani, & Nicoletta, 2021). In particular, instructional agents can be designed to simulate social interactions, which can facilitate learner engagement in learning tasks and thus enhance learning in a computer-based environment. By making the system more human, users can rely on standard interaction skills (e.g., interpreting each other's facial expressions or considering eye contact) (Reza, Christine, Ugan, & Rische, 2013), which allows for smoother interactions with the computer. This, coupled with increased motivation to interact with the system (due to higher levels of entertainment), can support cognitive functions such as problem solving, comprehension, and learning for learners, thus effectively enhancing learning and reading performance (Bhogal, Stone, Barlow, Kahlerz, Lestery, & Conversez, 1997; Dehn & van Mulken, 2000; Unalcolak & Ozan, 2012).

Data Analysis

The significant learning gains in teaching agent settings appear to be due to the social nature of teaching agent interactions and are empirically supported (Graesser, Moreno, & Marineau, 2003; Moreno et al., 2000). Some have examined the existence and purpose of social agents, and some have examined the benefits of natural language, which once had a dynamic, interactive presence.

Graesser, Moreno and Marineau (2003) found empirical support for the use of natural language and assessment as a way for students to model their knowledge and respond in a pedagogically appropriate manner. In this experiment, students participated in computer literacy tutoring through interactions with AutoTutor (Graesser et al., 1999). Conditions testing the effects of the dialog included tutoring interactions with either relevant (i.e., tested in the posttest) or irrelevant (i.e., not tested in the posttest) content areas. The results of the study indicated that participants who conversed with AutoTutor in the relevant domain condition showed higher learning gains than those in the irrelevant domain condition. The researchers concluded that AutoTutor's conversation-mediated behavior had a positive impact on learning.

Moreno et al. (2000) were interested in examining the benefits of programming for agents from the perspective of motivation and interest. Their hypothesis is that the inclusion of educational agents promotes learning gains through the phenomenon of social agency alone. Participants interacted with constructivist instructional programs through computers under different conditions. The conditions included an intelligent body environment versus a non-intelligent body environment, an animated intelligent body versus a human face, and auditory versus visual instructions.

Conclusion

The learning outcomes of this study showed significant differences in measures of transfer when learners were present in the learning environment. The researchers failed to find image effects when testing animated agents and videotaped humans. They also found that auditory instruction resulted in significantly higher memory compared to visual instruction. The study also showed that participants performed better in retaining, transferring and evaluating lessons when agents were taught in a personalized conversational style. These experiments support the phenomenon of learning through lively instructional tools in social settings. In the first two experiments, the authors concluded that their results support the use of instructional devices as a method to promote memory and transfer. More positive affective measures also suggest increased interest and motivation to learn under instructional conditions. The literature on educational agentic environments appears to be guided by advances in technology to create and implement them. Although empirical results are lacking to support the idea that agents themselves promote learning, the social aspects of instructional agent environments suggest that, when carefully designed, agents can serve as effective mentors or collaborators for students. Designers are working on student-centered learning environments that utilize a constructivist educational paradigm. With further advances in technology, it has become easier to create a dynamic, emotional conversation partner that can act as a mentor to students. These intelligent body environments offer a wide scope for further research, simply because of the rapid development of emerging technologies that allow for natural language processing and characters with human-like language and nonverbal communication.

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